

FROM SILENT TO STRONG: FEMINIST VOICES IN JANE AUSTEN'S
NOVELS

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Abstract. *Jane Austen's novels have always been in focus of attention and many scholars have studied her novels with a special interest. Female characters of Jane Austen are still studied since Jane Austen created those characters in her own witty style that is complex to understand for others. In her novels, "Sense and Sensibility", "Pride and Prejudice" and "Persuasion" Austen shows how female characters go through self-discovery being quiet and limited with social expectations, turn into strong and self-confident women. Taking these facts into consideration, in this article we decided to analyze features of feminism in Austen's heroines. Though there are some vivid elements of feminism in her novels, they are not considered as political but rather a literary foundation for feministic movement.*

Аннотация. *Романы Джейн Остин всегда привлекали внимание, и многие ученые изучали их с особым интересом. Женские персонажи Джейн Остин продолжают оставаться объектом исследований, поскольку писательница создала их в своем остроумном стиле, который сложно понять другим. В своих романах «Разум и чувства», «Гордость и предубеждение» и «Доводы рассудка» Остин показывает, как женские персонажи проходят через самопознание: будучи сначала тихими и ограниченными социальными ожиданиями, они превращаются в сильных и уверенных в себе женщин. Учитывая эти факты, в данной статье мы решили проанализировать черты феминизма в героинях Остин. Хотя в ее романах присутствуют явные элементы феминизма, они рассматриваются не как политические, а скорее как литературная основа феминистского движения.*

Annotatsiya. *Jeyn Ostinning romanlari doimo e'tibor markazida bo'lib kelgan va ko'plab tadqiqotchilar uning asarlarini alohida qiziqish bilan o'rgangan. Jeyn Ostinning ayol qahramonlari hali ham tadqiq etilmoqda, chunki yozuvchi ularni o'ziga xos, o'tkir aql bilan yaratgan bo'lib, bu uslub boshqalar uchun tushunish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin. U «Aql va hissiyot», «G'urur va xurofot» hamda «Ishontirish» romanlarida ayol qahramonlar qanday qilib o'zini anglash jarayonidan o'tib, dastlab jamiyatning ijtimoiy cheklovlari tufayli o'z ovozigga ega bo'lmagan bo'lsa-da, oxir-oqibat kuchli va o'ziga ishongan ayollarga aylanishini tasvirlaydi. Shu omillarni inobatga olgan holda, ushbu maqolada biz Ostinning qahramonlaridagi feministik*

jihatlarni tahlil qilishga qaror qildik. Uning romanlarida feminizmning aniq elementlari mavjud bo'lsa-da, ular siyosiy emas, balki feministik harakat uchun adabiy asos sifatida qaraladi.

Key words: *Feminism, female characters, self-discovery, self-determination, women's role, society.*

Introduction. Status of women is one of the central themes in Austen's novels. Austen was one of the first writers who introduced this theme to the literature. At the time when Austen lived, women had two roles: being a good wife and a mother. Women did not play an important role in the society: they could not vote. No one considered women as independent individuals who could express their ideas and tell their opinions. Through her six novels Austen wanted to change individuals' view on the status of women and women education. Austen's female characters challenge societal expectations through perseverance, intelligence, personal growth and compassion. "Jane Austen, like other female writers of the 19th century, rebelled against constraints placed on women through her novels".¹ Gilbert and Gubar argue that though many literary critics consider Austen's novels as domestic, they were powerful enough to address female agency and restrictions placed upon women. Moreover, Gilbert and Gubar see Austen's novels as a literary response to male writers who only depicted women as "angels" or "demons"; Austen could show how diverse can female characters be through her strong and witty female protagonists.

Methods. This article examines the language used to describe female characters and the time they lived to understand the challenges the female characters had at that time. The primary focus is on "Sense and Sensibility", "Pride and Prejudice" and "Persuasion" where Austen highlights the contrast between educated and uneducated women. The study also considers literary critiques and scholarly opinions, such as those of Brownstein, Gilbert, Gubar and Kirkham to assess Austen's influence on women empowerment.

Result. The analysis discloses that Austen's protagonists handle challenges in different ways but eventually grow from Silent to Strong and find their voices through self-discovery and personal growth.

1. Elizabeth Bennet (Pride and Prejudice)

Elizabeth Bennet is Jane Austen's the most independent character since she rejects two financially advantageous marriage proposals which were completely unaccepted and tragical at that time. She believes that marriage should be based on love, not

¹ Gilbert, S., & Gubar, S. "The Madwoman in the Attic: The woman writer and the nineteenth century imagination". Yale University Press, 2000.

financial security. Through this character Austen speaks up to all women who considered marriage as the only way to be secured financially.

2. Anne Elliot (Persuasion)

This protagonist is a brilliant example of growing from Silent to Strong since at the beginning of the novel Anne allows her family and friends to persuade her and cancel her engagement with Captain Wentworth because of low financial status. “Anne must learn to stop following the motherly advice of Lady Russel and marry as she herself sees fit”². However, Anne listens to her inner voice and begins to stand up for her choice.

3. Elinor Dashwood (Sense and Sensibility)

This character is different from others because of her quiet perseverance and emotional intelligence. She could govern her emotions even in the toughest situations. This can be observed when Elizabeth finds out that the man she loves, Edward is engaged to another woman, however, despite this heartbreak, she does not show her emotions and does not let her emotions to gain control over her. In the novel, Elinor represents “Sense” maintaining her dignity and resilience. She expresses her freedom through intelligence and direct speech.

Discussion

Elizabeth controls her feelings and accepts the situations as they really are. Elinor governs not only her own feelings but those of her sister and her mother. Jane Austen describes Elinor as following: “ Elinor’s feelings were strong but she knew how to govern them: it was a knowledge which her mother had yet to learn; and which one of her sisters had resolved never to be taught.”³. In “ Sense and Sensibility” Jane Austen portrays two female characters Elinor and Marianne who embody “Sense” and ”Sensibility”. Elinor represents sense with her self-discipline, prudence and a capacity to control her emotions while Marianne represents sensibility who is passionate, heart-guided and unable to control her emotions: “Elinor, this eldest daughter, whose advice was so effectual, possessed a strength of understanding, and coolness of judgment, which qualified her, though only nineteen, to be the counselor of her mother; she had an excellent heart; - her disposition was affectionate.”⁴ Aforementioned description of Elinor by Jane Austen presents a vivid image of a mature daughter, a caring sister and a rational thinker. The following excerpt taken from the novel clearly depicts Marianne Dashwood and demonstrates Marianne as an embodiment of sensibility. “Marianne’s abilities were, in many respects, quite equal to Elinor’s. She was sensible and clever; but eager in everything: her sorrows, her

² Brownstein, R. “ Becoming a Heroine: Reading about Women in novels”. Viking Press, 1997.

³ Auste,J. “Sense and sensibility”. Project gutenberg. 2010. -P 3.

⁴ Austen, Jane. Sense and Sensibility. Project Gutenberg. 2008.-P.3.

joys, could have no moderation. She was generous, amiable, interesting: she was everything but prudent.”⁵

These two strong female protagonists show Jane Austen’s witty studies about female characters and her contribution to bring women voices into English literature. A prominent English writer Sir Walter Scott evaluated Austen’s talent as following: “That young lady has a talent for describing the involvements and feelings and characters of ordinary life which is to me the most wonderful thing I ever met with.”⁶

Conclusion. Austen’s female characters prove that there are different paths to find one’s voice and it depends on the personality: one may choose direct and bold speech to gain self-empowerment while others may choose resistance, emotional intelligence or listening to inner voice. However, one thing is quite distinct: the path may be full of challenges, but eventually, if you do not betray your inner voice and speak your mind, you will find your place in society. Austen did not limit her heroines, there were no totally good or bad characters, instead Austen wanted to show how different female characters can be.

One more message that Austen wanted to convey through her characters is that women deserves love and mutual respect, it was quite more important than financial security.

Austen’s heroines are still powerful and eminent because they resonate to contemporary times. There are still some women who face challenges and pressures regarding marriage, education and career. These characters could be a glimpse of hope to women who need compassion.

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⁵ Austen, Jane. *Sense and Sensibility*. Project Gutenberg. 2008.-P.4.

⁶ Microsoft ® Encarta ® 2008. © 1993-2007 Microsoft Corporation. All rights reserved.